

The Optical to Mid-Infrared Extinction Law—An Adjustment to the Classic $R_V = 3.1$ Extinction Law

Shu Wang^{1,2}, Xiaodian Chen¹

¹ Key Laboratory for Optical Astronomy, National Astronomical Observatories, Chinese Academy of Sciences, People’s Republic of China

² Kavli Institute for Astronomy and Astrophysics, Peking University, People’s Republic of China

Abstract

The appropriate estimation and correction of extinction is critically important to interpret observations. With *Gaia* Data Release 2 (DR 2), we can determine the color excess ratios (reddening law) and the extinction ratios (extinction law) in high precision. We combine photometric, spectroscopic, and astrometric data to investigate the reddening and extinction law from optical to mid-infrared bands based on red clump stars. The *Gaia* bands are adopted as basis bands in determining color excess ratios and extinction ratios in a total of 21 bands. To better describe our observed extinction law, we adjust parameters of the classical $R_V = 3.1$ curve, together with the near-IR power-law index $\alpha = 2.07 \pm 0.03$. After analyzing the possible variations of color excess ratios, we concluded that based on the APOGEE sample, the extinction law is universal within 4 kpc and $A_V < 6$ mag.

1 Introduction

Interstellar extinction is the absorption and scattering of the starlight by dust. To interpret observations, the appropriate estimation and correction of extinction is critically important. As extinction and distance are often tightly coupled, correction for the extinction effects is also important to robustly anchor the distance scale. There are two indicators of extinction, the color excess ratio (CER) $E(\lambda - \lambda_1)/E(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)$, namely reddening law, and the relative extinction A_λ/A_{λ_1} , namely extinction law. With the knowledge of observed color indices and intrinsic color indices, the determination of CERs is straightforward. However, the calculation of the wavelength-dependent interstellar extinction law A_λ/A_{λ_1} is more challenging. It requires an independent determination of the extinction or the distance to the target. As a result, a fixed total-to-selective extinction ratio in the optical bands (e.g., R_V , R_I), or a fixed relative extinction in the near-infrared (IR) bands (e.g., A_J/A_{K_S} , A_H/A_{K_S}) is usually used to convert reddenings into the extinction law in the literature (e.g., Rieke & Lebofsky, 1985; Gao *et al.*, 2009; Zasowski *et al.*, 2009; Nataf *et al.*, 2013; Xue *et al.*, 2016, and references therein). However, the optical total-to-selective extinction ratio varies with interstellar environments (Cardelli *et al.*, 1989, hereafter CCM), and the near-IR extinction ratio also exists some uncertainties. The near-IR extinction follows a power law $A_\lambda \propto \lambda^{-\alpha}$. The index α reported in the publications ranges from 1.6 to 2.6 (Mathis, 1990; Draine, 2003; Nishiyama *et al.*, 2006; Stead & Hoare, 2009; Fritz *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2013; Wang & Jiang, 2014; Xue *et al.*, 2016; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Nogueras-Lara *et al.*, 2018; Matsunaga *et al.*, 2018; Hosek *et al.*, 2018). This means that the uncertainties of the index and the relative extinction are as large as 20%. In addition, when converting the near-IR CER to the α or the relative extinction, the selection of filter wavelengths (effective or isophotal) can lead to another $\sim 10\%$ discrepancy (Stead & Hoare, 2009; Fritz *et al.*, 2011; Wang & Jiang, 2014).

To complicate matters, some studies argued that the near-IR CERs are varied (e.g., Naoi *et al.*, 2006; Zasowski *et al.*, 2009), while some studies reported that the near-IR CERs are universal (e.g., Wang & Jiang, 2014; Chen *et al.*, 2018). In the literature, the values of near-IR CERs still have about 15% uncertainty.

The precise photometric data ($\sigma \lesssim 0.01$ mag) are helpful to derive accurate CERs (e.g., Schlafly *et al.*, 2016). However, to derive accurate extinction, accurate distance information is crucial. Previously, the accurate distances could only be derived in some special lines of sight, such as the Galactic center, clusters (Fitzpatrick & Massa, 2007; Fritz *et al.*, 2011; Daminieli *et al.*, 2016; Hosek *et al.*, 2018; Chen *et al.*, 2018). Thanks to the *Gaia* DR 2, it provides unprecedentedly accurate photometric data and good trigonometric parallaxes (Gaia Collaboration *et al.*, 2018; Lindegren *et al.*, 2018; Luri *et al.*, 2018). In our current work of Wang & Chen (2019), not only a much-improved extinction law is determined, but also some issues are revealed and discussed.

2 The Optical to Mid-infrared Extinction Law

We combine the photometric, spectroscopic, and astrometric data to investigate the optical to mid-IR extinction law. We adopted red clump (RC) stars as extinction tracers, which are selected by stellar parameters from the APOGEE survey. The multiband photometric data are collected from the *Gaia*, APASS, SDSS, Pan-STARRS1, 2MASS, and *WISE* surveys. By fitting the color–color or the color excess–color excess diagrams, the CERs are the slopes of the linear lines. However, due to the assumption of a static wavelength for each filter in determining the slopes, the CERs display different amounts of curvature at different bands, especially the broad *Gaia* bands. As the quality of the photometry improves, the curvature correction is needed to be considered. After subtracting intrinsic color indices and calibrat-

Figure 1: The optical to near-IR multiband extinction A_λ/A_V (red circles with error bars). Red line: our adjusted optical to near-IR extinction curves for $R_V = 3.1$; black line: the CCM $R_V = 3.1$ extinction curve.

ing the curvature of CER, we determined the CERs by fitting the color excess–color excess diagrams. The total uncertainties of our CERs are less than 0.015 based on elaborate uncertainties analysis and simulation analysis. Our CERs agree with previously published values, while the precision is significantly improved. With *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes, we independently calculate the extinction ratio $A_{G_{BP}}/A_{G_{RP}}$ between G_{BP} and G_{RP} bands. By combining the $A_{G_{BP}}/A_{G_{RP}}$ with the CERs, the relative extinction $A_\lambda/A_{G_{RP}}$ can be determined by $A_\lambda/A_{G_{RP}} = 1 + CER_\lambda \times (A_{G_{BP}}/A_{G_{RP}} - 1)$.

The extinction law is determined in total 21 bands from optical to mid-IR including two APASS bands (B , V), five SDSS bands (u , g , r , i , z), five Pan-STARRS1 bands (g , r , i , z , y), three *Gaia* band (G_{BP} , G , G_{RP}) three 2MASS bands (J , H , K_S), and three WISE bands ($W1$, $W2$, $W3$) (see Table 3 and Figure 9 of Wang & Chen (2019)). The precision of our new determined extinction law is much improved. Based on the definition of R_V , the ratio of the total-to-selective extinction $R_V = A_V/E(B - V) = A_V/(A_B - A_V)$, we derive the $R_V = 3.16 \pm 0.15$ for our extinction curve. Figure 1 shows the optical to near-IR multiband extinction A_λ/A_V (red circles with error bars). The black line is the CCM $R_V = 3.1$ extinction curve. Comparing it with CCM extinction curves, the CCM $R_V = 3.1$ extinction curve could only well explain this observed extinction law in the wavelength range of 300–550 nm ($< 2\%$ deviation). While at longer wavelengths, this new determined extinction law is significantly steeper than the $R_V = 3.1$ extinction curve. Especially in near-IR $0.9 \mu\text{m} < \lambda < 3 \mu\text{m}$, CCM extinction curves with power-law index $\alpha = 1.61$ cannot explain the quite steep trend. To better describe the observed extinction law, we made some adjustments of the parameters in the CCM extinction curve based on our extinction in optical and near-IR bands. For the R_V -dependent extinction law, the mean extinction takes the equations given below.

$$A_\lambda/A_V = A + B/R_V ; \quad (1)$$

Optical: $0.3 \mu\text{m} < \lambda < 1.0 \mu\text{m}$ and $Y = 1/\lambda(\mu\text{m}) - 1.82$,

$$A = 1.0 + 0.7499Y - 0.1086Y^2 - 0.08909Y^3 + 0.02905Y^4 + 0.01069Y^5 + 0.001707Y^6 - 0.001002Y^7 ; \quad (2)$$

$$B = (1.41338Y + 2.28305Y^2 + 1.07233Y^3 - 5.38434Y^4 - 0.62251Y^5 + 5.30260Y^6 - 2.09002Y^7) \times (1 - R_V/3.1) . \quad (3)$$

NIR: $1.0 \mu\text{m} \leq \lambda < 3.33 \mu\text{m}$,

$$A = (0.3722 \pm 0.0026)\lambda^{-2.070 \pm 0.030} ; \quad (4)$$

$$B = (-0.4728Y - 0.05932) \times (1 - R_V/3.1) . \quad (5)$$

These equations obey the form of the CCM model, while the coefficients are reanalyzed. Note that, the parameter B is zero when R_V equals 3.1. Figure 1 is the comparison of the adjusted $R_V = 3.1$ extinction curves (red line) to the CCM $R_V = 3.1$ (black line). The adjusted extinction curve is consistent with the observed extinction curve by better than 2.5% (Wang & Chen, 2019). This extinction curve can be used to predict relative extinction values for the future telescope, such as near-IR bandpasses of *JWST*. In our equations, the coefficients of Y^6 and Y^7 are negligible, and the coefficients of Y^4 and Y^5 are also small compared to those of CCM. This means that our curve is smoother than that of CCM (also seen in Figure 1), and the model of extinction curves could be simpler.

3 The Variation of Color Excess Ratio in the Galaxy

We determined the CERs for the RC sample that covered all the APOGEE fields. To explore the possible variation of CER $E(G - G_{RP})/E(G_{BP} - G_{RP})$ in the Galaxy, we measure this for each subregion. First, we divide the sight lines into some subregions based on the fields of the APOGEE survey. Each subregion covers $20^\circ \times 10^\circ$ and has at least 50 RC stars in general. Some regions have thousands of RC stars. Then, we measure the CER $E(G - G_{RP})/E(G_{BP} - G_{RP})$ for each subregion by linear fitting the color excess–color excess diagram after subtracting the intrinsic colors and correcting the curvature of the CER. The CER is the slope of the linear fit to the color excess–color excess diagram. Figure 2 shows the distribution of CER in the Galaxy for individual regions. Compared to the mean value of the Galaxy, the regions with CER discrepancy less than 2% are shown in black. The regions with large CERs errors are shown in red, and most of them are located in high latitude sight line with low extinction. These deviations from the average value can be fully explained by uncertainties. Hence, based on the APOGEE sample, the extinction law is universal ($d < 4$ kpc, and $A_V < 6$ mag). However, it is far from to say that the extinction law is common in everywhere of the Milky Way.

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Figure 2: The distribution of CER $E(G - G_{RP})/E(G_{BP} - G_{RP})$ for the different sight lines. Black: the region with CER deviation from the mean CER by less than 2%. Red: the region with large CER errors leading to the relatively large deviation to the mean value.

from the surveys by *Gaia*, SDSS, APOGEE, Pan-STARRS1, APASS, 2MASS and *WISE*. This work has made use of data from the European Space Agency (ESA) mission *Gaia* (<https://www.cosmos.esa.int/gaia>), processed by the *Gaia* Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC, <https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/gaia/dpac/consortium>). Funding for the DPAC has been provided by national institutions, in particular the institutions participating in the *Gaia* Multilateral Agreement.

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